

The Theories of Competitiveness and Stability

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Abstract:

The objective of this paper is to review the basic theories about competition, competitiveness, financial stability and theories about the effects of competitiveness on the level of financial stability. From there, we provide analysis and orientation for future research when studying the impact of competition, competitiveness on financial stability of businesses in general and commercial banks.

Keywords: Competitiveness, stability, theories

1. Introduction

For the economy, competition is not only the environment and the driving force to promote development in general, boost production and business, increase labor productivity, but also is an important factor in healthy social relations. Association, competition is also a condition to educate the dynamism of enterprises. Besides, competition contributes to evoke new needs of the society through the emergence of new products. That proves that people's lives are increasingly improved politically, economically and culturally. Ensuring competition promotes the development of science and technology, the division of radioactive labor develops deeply and broadly. However, in addition to the great benefits that competition brings, it still brings disadvantages such as unhealthy competition creating a differentiation between rich and poor, unhealthy competition will lead to fads. Violations of the law such as tax evasion, tax smuggling, counterfeiting, illegal trading of items prohibited by the State and law.

Any business too, when participating in business activities in the market, they want their businesses to survive and stand firm. In order to survive and stand firm, businesses must have specific and long-term strategic competition strategies on both the micro and the macro scale. They compete to gain advantages on their side, compete to win customers, make customers confident that their products are the best, suitable for their tastes, like the best consumer needs. Any enterprise that satisfies the needs of customers promptly, quickly and fully with products and services at appropriate prices will be able to survive and develop. Therefore, competition is very important and essential.

Competition requires businesses to develop marketing starting from market research to decide what to produce? how to produce? made for whom? Studying the field for enterprises to determine the market demand and only produce what the market needs, not what the enterprise has. Competition forces enterprises to offer higher quality products that are more convenient to consumers. To do that, enterprises must apply scientific and technical achievements to the production and business process, strengthen management, improve workers' skills, send staff to study to improve their qualifications. Specialize. The competition wins the business of creating a worthy position in the market, increasing the reputation for the business. On that basis, there will be conditions to expand production and business, reproduce society, create strong momentum for the economy.

The objective of this article is to review the fundamental theories about competitiveness, competitive advantage, and the stability of businesses in general and commercial banks in particular. The layout of the article outside the introduction includes: Research overview on the fundamental theories of competitiveness, stability; Theories about the impact of competitiveness on stability. And finally the conclusion and research direction in the future.

2. Literature review

2.1. Keynesian theory

According to this theory, high economic growth is always accompanied by inflation due to investment - saving is not necessarily in the moment. The government can proactively impact growth rates by pursuing an Inflationary finance policy that forces people to save, called forced savings to compensate into the gap between investment and savings. Therefore, the financial system plays a passive role in mobilizing savings and allocating resources. By dividing individuals into two categories: (i) the first with income per salary and (ii) the second with income per profit; Keynesian theory holds that a policy of high inflation and falling real interest rates will be more attractive to second-class individuals and therefore have a saving incentive to invest and reduce consumption. The first will experience a decline in real income, which encourages them to consume rather than save. The financial system is obliged to deposit savings from a second category of individuals until they have the resources to make a new investment. Thus, the financial system has a very passive role and it will only develop later if the economy develops sustainably. But growth policy based on inflation has been criticized in many ways: "There are unavoidable dangers associated with inflation-based growth policy. The biggest threat from the balance of payments if foreign currency is scarce. High inflation will put a heavy pressure on the country's balance of payments and the need for an import substitution policy or foreign exchange control, which leads to ineffective resource allocation. The threat to investment may be when inflation is too high, investment in machinery becomes unattractive compared to investment in the form of speculative investment in inventories, overseas assets. or real estate ...

2.2. Theory of Shaw and McKinnon

Contrary to Keynesian theory of the passive role of the financial system in promoting economic growth, theories support the view that the financial system has a positive role in promoting economic growth. The assumptions are shared by the financial system that the financial system is the best allocator of financial resources through risk-sharing and maturity transformation, and that under the same conditions as capital investment is similar. The most scarce counterpart is in poor low-income countries where a liberalized financial system will allocate resources most efficiently. In 1973 in "Money and capital in economic development", McKinnon, based on Shaw's point of view, introduced the theory of financial constraint and liberalization. The focus of this theory is that the government should not intervene in the financial system, but let them move on the basis of free markets. Thus the principle of effectiveness will be respected and financial resources will be allocated in the best way. McKinnon's theory is based on the assumption: investment and saving are both dependent on interest rates, in which: High interest rates increase savings (positive dependence). In addition, saving also depends on income. Investment is inversely dependent on interest rates. (Some government investments for public welfare are not considered in this theory.) McKinnon also points out that in most developing countries, governments often prefer to intervene in that country's financial system in order to keep real interest rates below competitive levels, restraining the financial system and no development. When interest rates are kept below equilibrium there is no allocation of resources, as some more profitable projects may not receive the capital investment, reducing the average return on investment. Thus, the economy will achieve slower growth than the results achieved when partially removing the interest rate control. Analysis of the McKinnon theory proves that when the financial system is constrained, investment decreases and government intervention is often ineffective. On that basis, McKinnon advised governments in developing countries not to interfere in their own financial systems and to let them operate according to the rules of the market or in other words to let the system. Financial liberalization. Thus, according to this theory, the financial system should develop first to promote economic growth, not a product of development. Today, this theory has been more or less accepted in developing countries and in the decades 1970-1989 a number of countries reformed the financial sector in the direction of easing government intervention in financial system.

2.3. Classic competition theory

Born around the eighteenth century in England, representing the classical competition theory school is the outstanding character Adam Smith (1723-1790). He said that competition with economy, if coordinated well in a reasonable way will bring many benefits to society: "If free competition, individuals squeeze each other, then

competition forces each other. the individual must try to do his job correctly ". Thus, A. Smith advocated individualism as the basis for all classical liberal economic arguments. Although each person is essentially for his own benefit, that benefit is consistent with the social interest. Thanks to competition, the acts are done in a harmonious way and increasingly promote the development of society. Therefore, free competition will help promote more efforts at work, constantly create to increase labor productivity, and increase the country's material wealth. In addition, freedom of competition can help to self-regulate the supply-demand relationship, and the output of the market through prices, organize a reasonable division of labor, thereby creating a balance in society. without the intervention of the State. Agreeing with A. Smith, John Stuart Mill also confirmed that competition contributes to social development. J.S. Mill emphasized individualism, but he argued that society should intervene to prevent individuals from having actions that cause negative consequences, even by force. K.Marx also contributed a lot in the system of theory of competition of this period. The main content of K.Marx revolves around the competition mainly taking place in three aspects: Price competition through increasing labor productivity; quality competition through enhancing the use value of goods; competition between industries through increased mobility to divide the surplus value. Thus, competition for capitalism in this period mainly occurred from the decision, implementation and distribution of surplus values.

2.4. Neoclassical competition theory

By the end of the nineteenth century and early twentieth century, capitalism had a drastic change to monopolistic capitalism. K.Marx's economic theory plays an increasingly important role in recognizing and evaluating economic phenomena. The classical economic doctrine seems powerless to defend capitalism. Economists have built a system of theories of competition on the basis of developing economic theories of earlier period. Typically: W.S.Jevons (1835 - 1882), A.Mashall (1842 - 1924) and L. Walras (1834 - 1910). The main purpose is to outline the basic principle of the movement of capitalism to navigate competition activities. The results of the studies in this period, also known as the neo-classical competition theory, give birth to a static approach to competition in four forms: Perfect Competition, Monopolist Competition, Monopoly and oligopoly.

2.5. Modern competition theory

If the neoclassical school sees competition as a static process, on the contrary, modern Austrian economists (typically Carl Menger, Eugen von Bohm - Bawerk, Friedrich von Wieser), that: the guiding ideology in modern competition theory is to eliminate the view of an ideal, ideal but unrealistic competitive market. Instead, competition is seen as a dynamic, evolving and constantly changing process. Thus, the pricing policy is no longer determined based on predetermined assumptions and premises, but must be placed under existing conditions. During the competition process, competitive elements are combined made possible with technical progress and innovation. The modern competition school theory is completely independent from the price and value of goods of the previous schools. In a nutshell, competition is simply an act of competition between actors and is seen as an attempt to come up with a way better than its competitors. According to modern competition theory, market information is inadequate. Producers play the role of allocating resources under limited conditions, in relation to the long-term relationship with consumers and owners of the resources. Therefore, competition promotes product innovation, innovation, corporate restructuring, rearrangement of production activities, finding and developing new markets for products

Many modern competition theories emerged such as the theory of Michael Porter, JBarney, P.Krugman ... In which, to mention the theory of "competitive advantage" of Michael Porter, he explains the phenomenon when the business is involved international trade competitors should have "competitive advantage" and "comparative advantage". He analyzed the competitive advantage that is the endogenous strength of the business, of the country, while the comparative advantage is the condition of natural resources, labor, and the environment to create favorable conditions for businesses and countries in in production but also in trade. Competition is the competition between individuals, collectives and economic units with equal functions through actions, efforts and measures to win the race, to satisfy the goals of me. These targets can be market share, profitability, efficiency, safety, brand

2.6. Theory of financial stability

Based on the economic theories of financial stability of economists such as Keney, Minsky, it can be seen that the center of the safety policies for the operation of the credit system are financial institutions, intermediaries, typically commercial banks. The main content of the policies is to focus on the results of the interaction between commercial banks with the financial market and the entire economy. Stemming from the process of forming, evolving and developing theories of financial instability and financial stability, banking stability theory is considered in terms of financial stability in banking operations, stems from the attempt to bring the bank out of financial instability, which is caused by the instability of the economy leading to the instability of the financial system.

Most studies on banking and financial stability are found to have rated "financial instability" as an approach to assessing "financial stability." Since then, the study has focused on volatility. Finance is the opposite state of financial stability. Theories of "financial instability" are researched and developed such as: The theory of financial instability of the Monetary school, The theory of financial instability of The Post Keynesian school, Minsky's Theory of Financial Instability, Koo's Theory of Financial Instability, ...

According to Keynes, the immediate changes in the short term manifested by phenomena such as inflation, unemployment or growth, ... are the causes of fluctuations in the financial system. Therefore, to intervene, it is necessary to implement fiscal and monetary tools to respond in a short time. He also emphasized the role of the government in regulating the above tools. In support of Keynes's ideology, developing from a Minsky point of view, Phase 2 is a risky time because investors increase leverage through borrowing from financial intermediaries. When the debt leverage exceeds the ability to bear the risks, it will lead to financial bubble burst, leading to debt crisis. Investors lose the ability to pay debts, damaging the capital of the economy. Therefore, the role of a financial intermediary at this stage is extremely important. Commercial banks need to regulate the amount of loan capital, based on comments and analysis of money supply and demand in the economy. The government also needs to intervene in the credit limit of commercial banks with appropriate monetary instruments. From there, reduce the pressure on the financial bubble in the future. Thus, both maintaining profitability for investors, ensuring stability for the financial system.

Bank stability theory from Minsky's point of view: Inheriting Keynes's point of view, Minsky pointed out the period of instability of commercial banks when investors increased speculative loans with expectations of high interest rates in the future. When the economy is unstable and the expected interest rates for investment opportunities are no longer available, investors tend to sell a wide range of assets to pay debts. At this time, the prices of financial assets also decreased because the valuation of commercial banks also decreased due to changes in the economy. A sudden decline in the value of a financial asset seriously affects the investor's stability and ability to repay debts. As a result, bank instability, liquidity affects, bad debt increases and mobilized capital is suddenly reduced. At that time, it was necessary to have the intervention of the government to restore the liquidity situation, settle bad debts, ... to bring the banking operations back to stability.

Based on the above directed economic ideology on banking and financial instability, modern economists have provided many empirical evidence for banking instability. There, the bank is considered a part of the financial market, so it is always directly and deeply influenced by the fluctuations of the national financial system in particular and the economy in general. According to (Davis, 2003), there are three types of financial instability: bank failure, volatile market prices and collapse that entails market liquidity. Therefore, banking stability plays a key role in financial stability. When banking was restored, the financial system recovered. At that time, the capital flow of the economy will be cleared, business will gradually stabilize. Research by (Garcia-Herrero, Del Rio Lopez, 2004) looked at the banking crisis as a proxy for financial instability. With their increasingly large and diversified development, financial institutions, especially banks, are always seen as a channel providing abundant capital sources for investors in the economy. In phase 2 of the "Minsky Moment", when investors want to increase debt leverage, investors tend to increase their bank loans more to finance investment opportunities. When the financial crisis occurs (phase 3 "Minsky Moment") leads to instability in the banking system due to a decline in the ability of customers to repay debts. At this time, the broken financial

bubble leads to difficulties for commercial banks, even banks at risk of bankruptcy because they do not recover too risky investment loans. Banking instability is widespread and can exacerbate economic instability. Another approach to banking stability through financial instability assessment is to find effective solutions to bring the bank back to a stable state, thereby identifying and evaluating the bank's tolerance threshold from steady-state state is also found in many previous studies.

A typical example is the study of (Edwin L.-C. Lai, 2002) on financial stability to find out the cause of bank instability is when the bank falls into liquidity crisis. At this point, the demand for liquidity in the short term exceeds the bank's existing capacity to reserve liquid assets. The weak bank's asset management has caused an imbalance between short-term liabilities (usually high proportion) and long-term assets (often a low proportion). In addition, the cause may also be due to high bank bad debts, impaired debt recovery, and customers' massive withdrawals when grasping information about weak financial and banking situations. , leading to the aggravation of banking turmoil. By a set of linear and non-linear methods, the author considers changes in the banking system over economic cycles, thereby placing each bank in a specific period, calculating and pointing The lower the probability of exhaustion leads to each bank, the higher the stability of the bank is.

3. Theoretical basis of the impact of competition on financial stability

Competition in the banking industry affects enterprises' ability to access capital, the stability of the financial sector and the economy with unclear direction. From a market position theory (Boyd, De Nicolo, 2005), a high position in the market allows banks to set higher interest rates, leading to increased risk of moral hazard and Adverse selection because only high risk companies accept high interest rates, it is also possible to increase the risk of capital return / profit for the bank. There are two opposing views in the studies of banking competition and stability.

3.1. Competitive perspective - vulnerable

It is argued that there is an inverse relationship between competition and banking stability, since high competition reduces the bank's market power and margins. Therefore, it will increase the risk for the bank. In other words, the greater the market power or the lower the level of market competition, the higher the bank's stability. Competition - instability model by Keeley (1990) and Marcus (1984) said that competition weakens the stability of the banking system. This relationship is expressed through a channel of franchise value. Increased competition will decrease the power of a bank to influence the market (Berger, Klapper and Turk-Ariss, 2008), thereby reducing the bank's brand value (Keeley, 1990). The lower the brand value of a bank, the lower its bankruptcy cost. Therefore, banks have an incentive to accept higher risks, thereby increasing the risk of bankruptcy. In addition to the charter value transmission channel, Allen and Gale (2000) found that, competition with the participation of many banks is ideal conditions for the spread of financial shocks. In addition to the direct effects, competition in the banking sector and market structure can also indirectly increase the risk-taking behavior of banks. Banking competition can create instability and, in turn, result in depositors / investors fleeing. Financial liberalization in the form of a gradual transition from monopoly to competition can increase vulnerability (Chang and Velasco, 2001). When the competition gets fierce, banks race on interest rates. This can bring benefits to customers, however, leaving banks at risk.

3.2. Stable-competitive perspective

The argument is that the more competition sees an inverse relationship between competition (measured by the number of participating banks) and the degree of risk in many leading to higher stability. (Stiglitz, Weiss, 1981) looks for banking. In a certain respect, if a bank encounters ethical risks leading to liquidity risk, the bank is at risk of bankruptcy in a full environment. Competition is essential for banks to better adapt their behavior and practices. Competition is necessary to enhance financial stability by overcoming the limitations of monopolistic markets (Caminal and Matute, 2002). The low centralization of the banking system limits the risk of a financial crisis. According to Boyd and Runkle (1993) and Mishkin (1999), this view is based on two main arguments - the problem is too big to collapse and the problem is too big to monitor. The first argument stems from the fact

that banks operating in an overly centralized market can become so large, so crucial to the economy, and so interconnected that the collapse of banks. This commodity tends to have a lasting effect on the real economy and costly social costs, thus forcing the government to bail out when these banks face the risk of bankruptcy. The possibility that large banks will be bailed out poses a problem of moral hazard as they are willing to take excessive risks knowing that they will be bailed by the government if they fail. This can make system stability fragile. The second argument is that the size of a bank is proportional to the degree of complexity, so small banks will be easier to manage and supervise than large banks. Large banks also often come with problems that are too large to monitor. This fact may encourage banks to take excessive risk because they know that regulators may not be able to detect the risk that banks are facing. Thus, the concentration and monopoly in the banking industry can negatively affect the stability of the banking system, or competition will help strengthen the stability of the banking system.

On the other hand, when information asymmetry occurs, higher competition reduces the ability of firms to access capital by making banks lose motivation to build credit relationships (Petersen, Rajan, 1994) and revenue. information collection (Robert Hauswald, Robert Marquez, 2006). On the contrary, when the competition is low, banks with high status tend to invest in learning and establishing close lending relationships with businesses because they are then easy to exploit the benefits from business support.

(Besanko, Thakor, 2004) shows that increasing competition reduces the information advantage from lending relationships and increases the risk taking behavior of banks. In addition, the competitive environment causes banks to receive less information about borrowers. Research by (Boot et al, 1993), (Allen, Gale, 2004) shows that banks will therefore have difficulty checking the credit profile of customers. The result is an increase in credit risk for banks and a high risk of volatility. Conversely, in a less competitive environment, banks are easier to provide credit for large loans, which increases the probability of banks collapsing (Caminal, Matutes, 2002). The reason can be explained that the high monopoly banking system allows banks to apply high interest rates, which means encouraging people to accept greater risks, making bad debt possible. However, high interest rates also bring high interest income for banks (Martinez, Miera, Repullo, 2010). It is this offset correlation that can create a nonlinear relationship between competition and banking stability. In addition, when there is less competition, banks with high profit margins facilitate capital accumulation to prevent abnormal shocks, reduce the incentive to accept high-risk projects, and reduce fluctuations in economic growth. health. In contrast, when the banking industry is in fierce competition, banks have low margins, insufficient capital reserves and are vulnerable to crisis.

4. Conclusion

Today, the trend of financial liberalization in the context of international economic integration to promote the expansion of trade activities to the world market is strongly supported. Commercial activities between countries are linked to the banking system of each country. The implementation of the trade agreements according to the committed contents will have a great impact on the national economy in general and the Vietnamese commercial banks in particular. Vietnam is considered one of the countries with the most free trade agreements signed today. In particular, the Large-scale Comprehensive and Progressive Agreement for Trans-Pacific Partnership (CPTPP) is assessed to bring great potential for development to 11 members, including Vietnam.

For Vietnam, the successful signing of the CPTPP agreement is a major milestone marking an important milestone for the transformation of the economy in general and the banking and financial sector in particular. The banking industry plays a vital role in the national economy. In all the signed contents directly related to the banking and finance sector, it is expected to bring great prospects for expanding investment and new financial services, but also the competitive pressure. forcing Vietnamese commercial banks to adjust and restructure themselves to suit the new situation.

With commitments to expand and remove barriers to entry among CPTPP member countries, there will certainly be the entry from foreign financial institutions with large scale, high expertise, and advanced technology. and diversified service types will enter the Vietnamese market. There have been many empirical studies showing that in the presence of foreign financial institutions, there will be many direct and indirect

impacts on the domestic commercial banking system, especially in two effects: spillover increases profitability and lowers operating costs; while the competitive effect will reduce profitability and operating costs. (Berger and Hannan, 1998). This could be a competitive pressure or destabilizing impact on banks, but at the same time it could also be an opportunity to access progress from the international community for domestic commercial banks. Therefore, in order to seize the opportunities and promptly respond to the challenges brought by the CPTPP agreement, Vietnamese commercial banks need to self-determine the current state of their competitiveness and stability. foreseeing competitive pressures as well as instability risks to have strategies to respond to challenges, improve competitiveness, consolidate and increase stability in banking operations in the context of CPTPP integration.

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